

used effectively to breed for grain protein (Fig. 1).

We grew 149 breeding lines of upland, lowland-upland derivatives, and lowland lines cultivated at an Ibaraki upland field in 1992. Chlorophyll content averaged 4.39 mg/100 cm² for upland rice and 4.03 mg/100 cm² for lowland-upland crossbred lines, which were significantly

higher than the 3.73 mg/100 cm² for lowland rice.

A negative correlation was observed between chlorophyll content and days to heading ($r = -0.448^{**}$). Early-maturing lines generally had higher protein content than late-maturing lines, although we found early-maturing lines with lower protein content in lowland-upland

crossbred lines (Fig. 2). We think that the low protein content was inherited from their lowland rice parents, although they have upland rice plant type, are tolerant of drought, and resistant to blast. These lowland-upland crossbred rice lines produce grain that is easy to process for rice crackers. The lines are also resources for breeding. ■

Grain quality of rice harvested at different maturities

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Harvesting rice at optimum maturity is important for obtaining high milling recovery and good cooking quality. We grew six commercial varieties in nonreplicated 600-m² plots during the 1989 and 1990 cropping seasons to study the effect of maturity stage on grain quality. The crop was kept flooded. The 50% flowering date was recorded.

Subplots of 6 m², replicated three times, were harvested from 27 to 42 d after flowering (DAF) at intervals of 3 d. Samples were sun-dried and milled 2 mo after harvest using Satake Rice Husking Machine Model THU-35A and Burrows McGill Polisher No. 3. Milled whole grains were cooked in excess water.

Grain maturity stage greatly affected rice quality (see table). We observed high total milled rice and head rice recovery with more elongation and less bursting/curling of grains upon cooking when the crop was harvested at 20-23% moisture. This level coincides with 33-36 DAF in all of the varieties except Basmati 198, which took 39 d.

Head rice recovery was low at both early and late maturity stages. Total milled rice and elongation ratio and bursting/curling upon cooking improved with delay in harvesting date up to 20-23% moisture, after which they leveled off. ■

Effect of harvesting rice at different stages of maturity on grain quality. RRI, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. 1989 and 1990.^a

Days to harvesting after 50% flowering	Moisture at harvest (%)	Milled rice recovery (% of rough rice dry weight)		Elongation ratio on cooking	Bursting/curling upon cooking (%)
		Total milled rice	Head rice		
27	27.8	68.02 c	49.62 d	1.702 d	11.90 a
30	25.3	69.13 b	52.75 bc	1.798 c	10.27 b
33	22.9	70.18 a	54.48 a	1.860 b	9.02 c
36	20.3	70.40 a	54.62 a	1.900 ab	8.38 cd
39	17.9	70.42 a	53.75 ab	1.908 ab	8.27 d
42	15.5	70.28 a	51.87 c	1.913 a	8.25 d
CV (%)	-	0.7	2.7	2.3	6.5
LSD (0.05)	-	0.59	1.71	0.05	0.72

^aMeans in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Relationship of Basmati 370 grain quality to soil and environment

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We conducted a pot experiment to study how soil and environment affect quality attributes and aroma development in Basmati 370. The crop was grown at Daska, a traditional rice-growing area, and Multan, a nontraditional rice-growing area of southern Punjab, during 1989 and 1990 dry seasons. See table for treatments. We evaluated the samples 3 mo after harvest.

Values for kernel length and length:breadth ratio were high in the Daska soil and environment sample (see table). Protein content was about the same across treatments. All samples had intermediate amylose and gelatinization temperature. Elongation and volume expansion ratios upon cooking were highest and aroma strongest in rice from Daska soil and environment. Aroma was

very poor in some samples and absent in the rice from Multan soil and environment.

We can conclude that rice from Daska soil and environment was better in cooked-rice cohesiveness and aroma than were any of the other samples. Aroma is the result of soil, environment, and plant type interaction. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. All field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Effect of soil and environment on quality attributes and aroma development in Basmati 370. Punjab, Pakistan, 1989 and 1990 dry seasons.^a

Treatment ^b	Physical dimensions			Chemical properties			Cooking characteristics				
	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Length: breadth ratio	Protein content (%)	Amylose content (%)	Alkali spreading value	Elongation ratio	Water absorption ratio	Volume expansion ratio	Cohesiveness score ^c	Aroma score ^e
Daska soil and environment	6.9 a	1.7 a	4.1 a	7.7 a	23.5 a	5.0 a	1.9 a	4.1 a	5.5 a	5.0 a	5.0 a
Multan soil and environment	6.6 a	1.8 a	3.7 a	7.8 a	21.5 a	4.2 a	1.6 a	3.9 a	4.8 a	3.0 c	1.0 c
Daska soil and environment	6.7 a	1.7 a	4.0 a	7.8 a	22.0 a	4.3 a	1.7 a	4.1 a	4.9 a	3.5 b	1.5 b
Multan soil and Daska environment	6.7 a	1.7 a	3.9 a	7.7 a	23.2 a	4.5 a	1.7 a	4.1 a	4.9 a	3.5 b	1.5 b
Pots transferred from Daska to Multan at PI ^b	6.7 a	1.7 a	3.9 a	7.7 a	22.5 a	4.5 a	1.7 a	4.1 a	4.8 a	3.5 b	1.6 b
Pots transferred from Daska to Multan at PE ^c	6.7 a	1.7 a	3.9 a	7.8 a	22.2 a	4.5 a	1.8 a	3.9 a	4.8 a	3.5 b	1.6 b
Pots transferred from Multan to Daska at PI ^b	6.6 a	1.7 a	3.9 a	7.7 a	22.6 a	4.6 a	1.7 a	4.0 a	4.8 a	3.5 b	1.6 b
Pots transferred from Multan to Daska at PE ^c	6.6 a	1.8 a	3.7 a	7.8 a	22.3 a	4.5 a	1.7 a	4.0 a	4.9 a	3.5 b	1.5 b

Results are av of 2 seasons. Means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^aPI = panicle initiation stage, PE = panicle exertion stage. ^cCohesiveness: 5 = well separated, 1 = pasty. ^eAroma: 5 = strong, 1 = absent.

Influence of degree of milling on grain quality characteristics of Basmati 385

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We studied the effect of varying milling pressure on grain quality characteristics of

Basmati 385, a commercially grown, fine-grain rice variety. The standard pressure used to mill Basmati 385 is 3.0 lb for 30 s.

Rice was dehulled using Satake Rice Husking Machine Model THU-35A. The hull percentage averaged 22.0. Brown rice samples, weighing 800 g, were milled at 10 pressures between 0.5 and

5.0 lb (0.5 lb increments) using McGill Polisher No. 3. Milling time was 30 s for each trial. The polished full grains were then cooked in excess boiling water. The experiment was repeated five times.

The percentages of total milled rice and head rice decreased gradually as milling pressure increased (see table). Cooked grain length was maximum (14.2

Grain quality characteristics of Basmati 385 at different milling pressures.^a RRI, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

Milling pressure (lb)	Milling recovery		Milled rice							Oil content of bran (%)
	Total (% of rough rice)	Head rice	Whiteness (%)	Cooked grain length (mm)	Bursting upon cooking (%)	Water absorption ratio	Volume expansion ratio	Protein content (%)		
0.5	71.5 a	60.8 a	36.0 h	13.6 d	7.0 a	2.45 d	3.50 d	9.2 a	20.95 a	
1.0	71.4 a	60.6 a	36.3 g	13.7 d	6.0 b	2.66 c	3.59 cd	9.0 b	20.60 ab	
1.5	71.4 a	60.4 a	36.6 f	13.8 cd	5.5 b	3.00 a	3.72 ab	8.7 c	20.58 b	
2.0	71.4 a	60.2 ab	36.8 e	14.0 abc	4.3 c	3.00 a	3.82 a	8.5 d	20.25 bc	
2.5	70.9 ab	59.5 b	37.0 d	14.2 a	3.5 cd	3.03 a	3.76 ab	8.3 e	20.10 cd	
3.0	70.5 bc	58.1 c	37.4 c	14.2 a	3.5 cd	2.97 a	3.70 b	8.1 f	20.00 cd	
3.5	70.4 bc	56.4 d	37.5 c	14.1 ab	3.0 d	2.90 ab	3.70 b	8.1 f	20.00 cd	
4.0	70.2 bc	56.0 d	37.7 b	14.1 ab	2.5 e	2.87 ab	3.65 bc	8.0 f	19.90 cd	
4.5	69.9 c	54.5 e	38.0 a	14.0 abc	1.5 f	2.75 bc	3.53 d	8.0 f	19.85 d	
5.0	69.7 c	53.0 f	38.0 a	13.9 bc	1.0 f	2.75 bc	3.57 d	8.0 f	19.80 d	

Means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.